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What makes an app authentic? Determining antecedents of perceived authenticity in an AI-powered service app

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ABSTRACT

Mobile applications integrated with artificial intelligence play a vital role in engaging users with the services thanks to their ability to perform natural interactions and conduct various tasks. Despite users' quest for authenticity, limited studies have explored the notion of authenticity of this non-human humanlike touchpoint. Study 1 (n = 331) explores the four dimensions of authenticity in the context of AI-powered service apps. Using regulatory engagement and parasocial interaction theory, study 2 (n = 309) confirms media richness, parent brand attitudes, and co-branding fit as influencing factors of perceived authenticity in the context of AI-powered service apps. The six solutions from fsQCA reveal the different but equally important combinations of media, brand, endorser, and personal factors to achieve a high perception of authenticity. This study contributes to the algorithmic experience literature by extending the idea of "proper means" in the AI-powered context.

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) technology is integrated into a channel to "touch" users throughout the customer journey (Bock, Wolter, & Ferrell, 2020). Ten years ago, when Amazon developed its famous virtual assistant, Alexa, users found it easier to search for relevant songs, movies, or shopping products (Alimamy & Kuhail, 2023). Since then, more companies have leveraged AI technology for service encounters (Breneman, De Gauquier, Willems, & Vanderborght, 2021), service recoveries (Jones, Hancock, Kazandjian, & Voorhees, 2022), and task-related conversational agents (Alimamy & Kuhail, 2023; Wirtz et al., 2018). For example, healthcare services such as Northamptonshire Healthcare National Health Service and Prudential utilize AI conversational agents to increase physical and mental health support (Deswal, 2023). Beauty services such as Sephora and Neutrogena use virtual assistants to scan users' faces and recommend relevant make-up products. When integrating AI technology into mobile apps, these apps can act as sales representatives to introduce new products, give recommendations, and close sales while displaying the brand identity (Jones et al., 2022). Online chat services that AI agents manage to save \$8 billion annually for service firms (Wirtz et al., 2018).

Despite the advancement of technology, AI-powered services do not

support the decision-making processes purely through technical reasoning but also reflects and reproduces social dynamics that are intertwined with technical, cultural, and legal issues (Shin, 2023). Customers may not understand how AI-powered service apps learn and make decisions, leading to higher degrees of uncertainty (Bock et al., 2020). Algorithms may also raise social and ethical issues when they mislead customers or provide inaccurate recommendations (Shin, 2023). The sophisticated condition of algorithm technology emphasizes the importance of algorithmic experience – how people experience and perceive algorithms in AI-powered services.

Recent research has explored the contributing factors to algorithmic experience (Ameen, Tarhini, Reppel, & Anand, 2021; Shin & Park, 2019). Algorithmic experience can be enhanced based on customers' interpretation of the algorithm's fairness, transparency, and accountability, along with its usefulness and ease of use (Shin & Park, 2019). Personalization and accuracy are crucial contributors to algorithmic service success (Ameen et al., 2021); however, customers are progressively becoming more aware of their data (Sax, Helberger, & Bol, 2018). In other words, customers decide to engage with the algorithms when they find the algorithmic experiences are authentically generated (Alimamy & Nadeem, 2021). Algorithmic experience can not only be enhanced through the algorithm's usability (e.g., personalization,

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accuracy) but also through cognitive, and affective dimensions of customer experience (e.g., fairness, respect for privacy rights, transparency). Aligning with this extant research, we aim to further explore the factors that make users accept, use, and interact with the algorithm system.

The proliferation of AI-powered services has brought the authenticity crisis (Alimamy & Kuhail, 2023; Italie, 2023; Jones et al., 2022; Vo et al., 2023). In the human context, Taylor Swift and Prince Harry have publicly sought to embody authenticity in their language and actions. Similarly, Elon Musk emphasized the importance of authenticity in on-line communication, encouraging leaders to "speak authentically" on social media platforms (Italie, 2023). However, no prior empirical investigation has explored the role of authenticity in determining preference for or resistance to AI-powered service apps. As previous studies have drawn on perceived value, attitude, intention to use, trust (Shin, 2020a), personalization, and accuracy (Ameen et al., 2021) to investigate the contributing factors of algorithmic experiences, this study extends the research vein by drawing on the concept of authenticity. The following research questions guide this study:

- RQ1: How do users construe a perception of authenticity in the context of AI-powered services, and what is the role of authenticity in the engagement process?
- RQ2: What are the antecedents of that perception of authenticity?

This research addresses three limitations of previous studies. First, it explores the concept of authenticity in AI-powered service apps, which are often referred to as conversational ability but ignore the importance of the "self" that distinguishing humanlikeness and authenticity (Alimamy & Kuhail, 2023; Jones et al., 2022; Whang & Im, 2021). Second, although research has explored the outcomes of authenticity in various contexts, the specific factors that contribute to AI service authenticity are underexplored. Third, previous studies have focused on individual AI agents (e.g., chatbots; conversational agents) rather than the entire service touchpoint, such as AI-powered apps, which involve multiple user interactions (e.g., welcoming, providing personal information, talking with AI agents, getting recommendations, and placing orders) (Alimamy & Kuhail, 2023; Rese, Ganster, & Baier, 2020). This research examines AI-powered service apps, addressing the need for insights into enhancing user engagement through apps (Mondal & Chakrabarti, 2021; Rosado-Pinto & Loureiro, 2020).

The existing studies shed light on the conceptualization of

authenticity in the AI service app context and its antecedents. The purpose of this study is three-fold: (1) to explore the conceptualization of authenticity from the multidimensional perspective, (2) to define the antecedents, moderators, and outcomes of authenticity, and (3) to explore the combination of antecedents influencing the perception of authenticity in the context of AI-powered service apps. Using heuristic-systematic model of the algorithmic process (HSM) (Shin, 2023), regulatory engagement theory (Pham & Avnet, 2009) and parasocial interaction theory (Horton & Richard Wohl, 1956), we show that variables related to other attributes such as brand, media, and social norms can impact the users' perception of the AI service app's authenticity, and subsequently, behavioral intention (see Fig. 1). The findings help advance the technology engagement studies by defining the authenticity of AI-powered service apps and highlighting their importance in leading to the intention to use and value co-creation intention.

2. Theoretical background and hypothesis development

In this research, we integrate insights from the heuristic-systematic model of the algorithmic process (HSM) (Shin, 2023), parasocial interaction theory (PSI) (Horton & Richard Wohl, 1956) and regulatory engagement theory (RET) (Higgins & Scholer, 2009; Pham & Avnet, 2009) as the theoretical frameworks. While the Heuristic-Systematic Model of the algorithmic process provides a framework for examining the cognitive processes that lie behind customers' elaboration of authenticity, PSI and RET guide our hypothesis on the antecedents and consequences of perceived authenticity.

2.1. Conceptualizing service app's authenticity in a technology context

Authenticity has been defined as genuineness, reality, truth, sincerity, or originality (Beverland & Farrelly, 2010). However, such synonyms do not fully explain the concept (Moulard, Raggio, & Folse, 2020). Previous research has not provided numerous meanings of authenticity, leading to the ambiguity surrounding the concept (Moulard et al., 2020). Moulard et al. (2020) then developed the Entity-Referent Correspondence Framework that proposes an overarching definition of authenticity - authenticity as a consumer's perception of the degree to which an authentic entity corresponds with or is "true to" a referent. True-to-idea (TTI) refers to how a product or service's attributes match societal norms and standards of how things "ought to be", true-to-fact (TTF) refers to the correspondence between

Fig. 1. The conceptual model.

the product and their offerings, and true-to-self (TTS) is the degree that an entity being intrinsically or extrinsically motivated (Moulard et al., 2020). Table 1 summarizes the conceptualization of the authenticity concept in brand and marketing studies and the relevant classification based on the ERC framework.

The review of authenticity conceptualization in marketing studies (Table 1) shows that most conceptualization studies draw on the brand, virtual tourism, employee, and influencer context, which creates a lack of knowledge on how this notion is evaluated in the context of AI-

Table 1
Review of authenticity conceptualization.

Studies	Dimensions	Explanations	Classification
(Kumar & Kaushal, 2021; Morhart et al., 2015)	Continuity	The ability to go beyond trends and embracing timelessness and historicity	TTI
	Credibility	The ability to upkeep the promises	TTF
	Integrity	The display of moral pureness and virtue, along with responsibility	TTS
	Symbolism	Users can define who they are by using a brand	TTS
Kim et al. (2020)	Quality	Brand is a potent symbol of continued quality	TTF
	Commitment	Emits a sense of continuity.	TTI
	Heritage	Refuses to sacrifice their values	TTS
	Sincerity	Comes off as very genuine	TTS
Lee and Eastin (2021)	Truthful endorsement	Gives very honest reviews on brands	TTF
	Visibility	Reveals a lot of their personal life to the public	TTI
	Expertise	Is skilled in their field	TTF
	Uniqueness	Has distinctive characteristics	TTI
	Real	Virtual tourism is authentic if it makes people feel they are in the real place	TTI
Mura et al. (2016)	Accuracy	Reliable in terms of what it conveys to users.	TTF
	Integrity	Being intrinsically motivated (not for financial purpose)	TTS
Nunes et al. (2021)	Legitimacy	Conform to established norms, standards, regulations, or traditions.	TTI
	Originality	Differentiate oneself from existing market offerings.	TTI
	Proficiency	Demonstrate appropriate skills, craftsmanship, and/or expertise.	TTF
	Connectedness	The user feels engaged, familiar with, and sometimes even transformed	TTS
	Social presence	The AI-powered service app is authentic when it shows assistant-like characteristics and makes people feel they are in a real place.	TTI
Proposed for this study	Credible	An app is authentic if it is reliable and provides what it claims.	TTF
	Integrity	An app is true to the brand's value. It has the users' best interests in mind and not be guided by ulterior motives.	TTS
	Symbolism	The app is authentic if it symbolizes the person a user is and positively impacts what others think of that user.	TTS

Notes: TTI = True-to-ideal; TTF = True-to-fact; TTS = True-to-self.

powered services.

In technology studies, authenticity has been conceptualized as the AI agents' ability to communicate naturally (Kuhail, Thomas, Alramlawi, Shah, & Thornquist, 2022; Rese et al., 2020; Wuenderlich & Paluch, 2017) (Table 2). In other words, authenticity has been referred to as humanlikeness (Glikson & Asscher, 2023; Neururer, Schlögl, Brinkschulte, & Groth, 2018; Wuenderlich & Paluch, 2017), suitable visual representations (Rese et al., 2020), conversational ability, transparency, learning from experience (Neururer et al., 2018), gender and race-matching (Jones et al., 2022).

Acknowledging the limitations of the anthropomorphism approach to authenticity, recent research has suggested different dimensions of this concept (Pentina, Hancock, & Xie, 2023; Vo, Dang-Pham, Hoang, & Nguyen Van Thang, 2022). Studies have found a relationship between agents' characteristics, such as transparency, the reflection of users' values and identification, and desirable behavioral outcomes (Neururer et al., 2018; Pentina et al., 2023; Sax et al., 2018). When the AI agent does not show any favoritism or discrimination, and the algorithmic decision is interpretable to people, customers will trust its decision (Shin & Park, 2019). Thus, to explore the notion of authenticity in AI-powered services, we need to broaden the traditional assumptions that we desire service from "someone like us" and consider other factors that relate to customer experience, such as credibility, sincerity, integrity, accuracy, and connectedness (Kim, Kim, Holland, & Townsend, 2020; Kumar & Kaushal, 2021; Morhart, Malär, Guèvremont, Girardin, & Grohmann, 2015; Nunes, Ordanini, & Giambastiani, 2021).

In their recent research, Shin has developed a heuristic-systematic model of the algorithmic process that suggests a dual route of influence of fairness, transparency, and accountability on users' intention in algorithm systems (Shin, 2023). In the heuristic-systematic model of information processing, while information is processed through easily comprehended cues that activate well-learned judgmental shortcuts in heuristic responses, users attempt to thoroughly understand any available information through careful attention, deep thinking, and intensive reasoning in systematic responses (Todorov, Chaiken, & Henderson, 2002). From this lens, fairness, accountability, and transparency are heuristic cues that support users to process large amounts of generated information (Shin, Koerber, & Lim, 2024); while the accuracy and personalization of the system are evaluated through systematic development (Shin, 2023).

Drawing on this framework, we investigate the perception of authenticity when customers interact with AI-powered services. When they are presented with the AI-powered service app, heuristic assessment involves evaluating the available cues such as social presence and integrity, while customers employ systematic processing to critically assess information by evaluating its credibility and symbolism.

Social presence. Social presence relates directly to the ability of the virtual environment to describe something real (Alimamy & Nadeem, 2021). The technology must mimic or simulate the experience in the bricks-and-mortar environment to authenticate the offline experience (Bregman et al., 2021). Because customers may not have the ability to understand the underlying mechanisms of the conversational AI agents in the AI-powered service app, they normally rely on the agent's behavior that portrays human traits such as feelings (Hsieh & Lee, 2021) and behaves conversationally. The agent's appearance, voice, dress, and gestures could work as the heuristic for customers to judge the authenticity of the app in general.

Integrity. Integrity refers to the extent to which an AI service app shows real care to users without exploitative intention. It describes the customers' feeling of confidence that the algorithm in the apps will perform actions that are genuinely beneficial to them rather than exploiting their data (Morhart et al., 2015; Shin, Lee, & Hwang, 2017). The integrity cues can be heuristic because customers do not have information to examine the intention of the developers. Thus, they may rely on the product placement in the recommendation or in-app advertising (Sax et al., 2018). To ensure authenticity, agents must

Table 2
The review of the authenticity of technology device.

Reference	Technology	Theory	Authenticity definition	Key findings
Alimamy and Kuhail (2023) Rese et al. (2020)	Intelligent virtual assistants Online retail CAs	Stimulus-Organism-Response theory Technology Acceptance Model and Uses and Gratifications	The ability to communicate authentic, natural, exceptional, and genuine information. The chatbot's ability to communicate naturally.	Authentic experiences lead to trust and commitment, involvement, and usage intention. Authenticity increases user acceptance.
Kuhail et al. (2022) Jones et al. (2022)	An academic advising system Chat-based avatar in service recoveries	The Big Five Inventory Communication accommodation theory	The ability to have a humanlike conversation and display a clear purpose The service agent is a real individual with the capability to feel and experience empathy while communicating in a natural manner	Personality affects the perceived authenticity. Avatar authenticity can be enhanced when the avatar is female, and when the avatar is dressed professionally or of a different race than the consumer.
Wuenderlich and Paluch (2017)	AI-based communication	No theory	Users evaluate service agents as more authentic when they have human nature.	Agent-related cues (visual, identity, audio cues) and communicative capability lead to perceived authenticity.
Neururer et al. (2018)	Chatbot	No theory	Five agent authenticity traits are transparency, learning from experience, coherency, conversation, and anthropomorphism.	Agent authenticity supports a better coexistence of artificial intelligence technology with its users.
Pentina et al. (2023)	Social chatbot	Human-computer interaction and interpersonal relationship theory	Authenticity (agency/autonomy/uniqueness)	AI authenticity is positively related to AI social interaction, leading to attachment.
This study	<i>AI-powered service app</i>	<i>Regulatory engagement and Parasocial interaction theory</i>	<i>Authenticity refers to the extent to which the apps can provide credible, integrity, symbolic, and humanlike experiences.</i>	

show “how they behave in specific situations, how they make decisions following some ethical standard” ([Neururer et al., 2018](#)), in which any outputs produced by an algorithmic system should be explainable ([Shin, 2021](#)). The lack of transparency inferred manipulative intent and led to perceived inauthenticity ([Alimamy & Nadeem, 2021](#); [Shin & Park, 2019](#)).

Credibility. The credibility dimension refers to an AI service app’s ability to provide reliable information ([Morhart et al., 2015](#)). Credibility is the reputation of such apps impacting the ability to be believed; it is the extent to which a user considers the information presented by the app to be believable, trustworthy, accurate, fair, objective, and reliable ([Shin, 2021](#); [Wang, Molina, & Sundar, 2020](#)). Without credibility, customers lack the confidence and assurance they need to be willing to be vulnerable to the recommendations that the apps provide ([Hsieh & Lee, 2021](#); [Shin et al., 2017](#)). As a part of a systematic process, the evaluation of credibility does not only encompass the evaluation of a message’s arguments but also includes verifying the information validity. An AI service app is credible if it can fulfill its promises. Customers often employ an in-depth analysis to verify the recommendation’s validity before trusting the app.

Symbolism. Symbolism refers to how an AI service app reflects values consumers consider essential and helps them construct who they are. The AI service app should be able to serve as a resource for identity construction by providing self-referential cues representing values, roles, and relationships ([Vo et al., 2022](#)). In that sense, the app is authentic if it has no favoritism and does not discriminate against people ([Shin, 2020a](#)), which shows the respect of the apps for users’ values and identities. The recommendation from the app brings symbolic value when it reflects customers’ personalized preferences and matches their needs ([Ameen et al., 2021](#); [Shin, 2020a](#); [Whang & Im, 2021](#)). This involves a performative evaluation of personalization and self-reflection.

H1. The authenticity perception of AI-powered service includes four dimensions of social presence, integrity, credibility, and symbolism.

2.2. Theoretical foundations of apps authenticity for consumer responses

This study uses a combined theoretical frame that integrates regulatory engagement theory (RET) and parasocial interaction theory. The RET is utilized to highlight the element of authenticity in the multidimensional view and predict user engagement at a behavioral level

([Higgins & Scholer, 2009](#); [Pham & Avnet, 2009](#)), and parasocial interaction theory is used to explain user-app relationships, as it views AI-powered services as a relationship partner that can be engaged through their physical and task attraction ([Whang & Im, 2021](#); [Youn & Jin, 2021](#)).

2.2.1. Regulatory engagement theory

The regulatory engagement theory (RET) provides a theoretical framework to predict the engagement of an object using the goal-pursuit process ([Higgins & Scholer, 2009](#); [Pham & Avnet, 2009](#)). The theory posits that the experience of the motivational force is one of the sources of value experience ([Higgins & Scholer, 2009](#); [Pham & Avnet, 2009](#)). “Proper way” has been considered as a source of motivational force experiences, which highlights that the value gets during the goal-making process does not rely on the value of the outcomes ([Higgins, 2006](#)). Individuals tend to engage more strongly in the activities if they see the value of the means, and that means deriving their appropriateness to his or her situated identity (e.g., meeting norms and following standards of appropriate conduct) ([Higgins, Camacho, Idson, Spiegel, & Scholer, 2008](#)). [Kirk, McSherry, and Swain \(2015a\)](#) draw on this notion to propose that when individuals focus on proper decision-making (“deciding the right way”), psychological ownership of an investment will be greater when their decisions are congruent (versus incongruent) with a nonconsciously activated goal.

This study conceptualizes authenticity as the “proper means” in the goal-pursuit process. If the app is inauthentic, it provides customers with non-credible, commercialized, and biased information ([Sax et al., 2018](#)). Customers, therefore, will make their health decisions mistakenly. The apps will become unethical and identity-threatened touchpoints, which may lead to brand abandonment ([Feng & Xie, 2018](#)). In other words, customers use the apps (e.g., the means) to eventually get the brand information and receive recommendations (e.g., the goal). Thus, when customers can decide using means that feels proper and right (e.g., the app is credible, humanlike, integrity, and symbolism), their attention is directed inward, enhancing the association with self and identity ([Kirk, McSherry, & Swain, 2015](#)). Engagement will occur, where the value of both brands and customers could be exchanged and co-created. Scholars have also used RET to explain the relationship between customer engagement via technology and brand usage intent ([Arghashi & Yuksel, 2022](#)); to determine the impact of perceived control on food consumption ([Lunardo, Jaud, & Jaspers, 2022](#)); to confirm the effect of the proper

decision-making process on psychological ownership and word-of-mouth intentions (Kirk, Swain, & Gaskin, 2015).

2.2.2. Parasocial interaction theory

Parasocial interaction is a one-sided interpersonal relationship that television viewers establish with media characters (Horton & Richard Wohl, 1956). During the exposure, viewers will analyze shared experiences, and a bond of intimacy interpreted by appearance, gestures, voice, and conversation to decide to continue a parasocial relationship or not (Horton & Richard Wohl, 1956; Rubin & McHugh, 1987).

A key element in the user–figure relationship is authenticity/realism (Giles, 2002). A popular celebrity can easily harm this parasocial relationship by endorsing an inappropriate product (Giles, 2002). However, the role of authenticity/realism in parasocial relationships has been recently reconsidered and extended as modern technology emerges. Real-life characters in the media are either recorded or imitated (e.g., by actors); intense parasocial attachments may be formed with figures who are not “authentic,” such as a pop star who takes an obvious pseudonym and is only known through his or her “act,” or a cartoon character (Giles, 2002). In the field of computer-mediated communication where media provides characters moderated or completely generated by technology (e.g., virtual influencers, websites, chatbots) (Whang & Im, 2021; Youn & Jin, 2021), authenticity refers to human qualities like consciousness and responsibility (Han & Yang, 2018; Whang & Im, 2021). Parasocial relationships with authentic artificial characters increase communication intimacy, leading to brand likability, intention to use, evaluation of the recommended product, and satisfaction (Han & Yang, 2018; Whang & Im, 2021).

Previous studies have examined the importance of task, and physical attraction for the development of parasocial relationships (Rubin & McHugh, 1987). Physical attraction is based on “dress and physical features” of the objects (Rubin & McHugh, 1987). In the technology context, physical attraction can refer to the media design (e.g., colors, vividness), functions (e.g., sounds, tone of voice) or anthropomorphized qualities (Whang & Im, 2021). Task attraction refers to the viewer’s perception of how easy or worthwhile working with the media character would be. For example, customers develop a long-term relationship and commitment with anthropomorphized objects as they imbue the object with consciousness and responsibility to perform the task (Whang & Im, 2021). In this research, media richness could be considered a physical attraction, in which the use of text, voice, and AR may bring different judgments about the imagined appearance of the AI agent. Parent brand attitude and co-brand fit, which signals the app’s ability to complete a goal– are conceptualized as task attraction.

2.3. Potential factors influencing authenticity perception

2.3.1. Media richness

Media richness refers to the app’s ability to transmit a variety of different cues such as sounds, images, and video clips, use rich and varied language, design messages to own or others’ situations, and convey multiple types of information (Hsieh & Lee, 2021). An AI service app could interact with users in two-way conversations using text-based (e.g., WYSA), text-images-videos (e.g., Ada), voice-audio (e.g., Siri, Google Assistant, Alexa), or text-voice-augmented reality (e.g., Replika). In high-involvement services such as healthcare, 3D visualization in AR and VR technology enables a person to interact with a computer using bodily sensations and movements, providing users with a vivid and immersive experience (Bregman et al., 2021; Chung, Kramer, & Wong, 2018). In their interaction with an AI service app, media richness is a key determinant affecting the establishment of trust, which, in turn, affects attitude, continued usage intentions, and online purchase intentions through AI assistants (Hsieh & Lee, 2021). If the media is rich, sufficient, and accurate, users may perceive that the AI service app is more concerned with the accuracy of their answers to provide a good health diagnosis, which may increase perceived authenticity.

H2. Perceived media richness is positively associated with perceived authenticity.

2.3.2. Parent brand attitude and brand-app fit

Users frequently rely on the brand name as an extrinsic signal to develop their initial trust in the app context (Spiggle, Nguyen, & Caravella, 2012). Users unfamiliar with the app often refer to the brand factors to evaluate its authenticity (Vo et al., 2023). For example, Zhang and Patrick (2021) show that brand nickname use in user-generated content signals the “inferred brand attachment”, boosting perceived information authenticity. Similarly, Childs, Woo, and Kim (2019) find that the type of brand will influence users’ perceptions of brand authenticity.

The app is an associated touchpoint with its parent brand (Iyer, Davari, & Mukherjee, 2018). The quality of an extension is often associated with the quality of the parent brand. In other words, a medium-quality extension may lower the quality associations of the parent brand and result in a less favorable attitude toward the brand. On the other hand, when a familiar and high-quality brand introduces its new products, users may have fewer concerns about that product (Zimmer & Bhat, 2004). Therefore, we hypothesize that:

H3. Users’ positive attitude toward the parent brand is positively associated with perceived authenticity.

The literature has identified co-branding fit as the relevancy between the brands’ images within the partnership, which influences the effectiveness of those partnerships (Ilicic, Baxter, & Kulczynski, 2018). Co-branding fit means the brand alliance is meaningful, logical, complementary, and congruent (Bigné, Currás-Pérez, & Aldás-Manzano, 2012; Bigné, Currás-Pérez, & Aldás-Manzano, 2012). Such fit has been found to influence perception and purchase intention positively (Bigné et al., 2012; Ilicic et al., 2018). This research views co-branding fit as the extent to which the co-brand has the appropriate expertise and skills to achieve the app’s goals (Iyer et al., 2018). If the parent brand and brand extension portray the “match-up,” users believe that the app can finish the tasks while remaining true to itself, maintaining what it stands for, and not exploiting the consumer (Spiggle et al., 2012). Therefore, we hypothesize:

H4. Perceived co-branding fit is positively associated with perceived authenticity.

2.3.3. Health consciousness and endorsement credibility

Health consciousness reflects a person’s awareness of his or her health conditions and willingness and readiness to be healthier (Chen & Lin, 2018). It was considered a predictor of health attitudes and behaviors (Chen & Lin, 2018). Individuals with a higher health consciousness are more likely to be involved in fitness, nutrition, and stress management activities (Ahadzadeh, Pahlevan Sharif, & Sim Ong, 2018). They are more critical of any health-related information (Ahadzadeh et al., 2018). When they use AI-powered health apps, they may be more skeptical about the app’s intention, the genuineness of the offerings, or the credibility of the recommendation.

H5. Health consciousness moderates the relationship between (a) media richness and perceived authenticity, (b) between parent brand attitude and perceived authenticity, and (c) between co-branding fit and perceived authenticity of an AI service app.

Earlier research on endorsement credibility suggests that a credible and trustworthy source is the significant factor that leads to the positive evaluation of the new touchpoint (Jung & Kellaris, 2006). Further, there is a strong link between endorsement credibility and authenticity perception. Authenticity is in the eye of the beholder, and the norms regulating what is deemed authentic are typically an outcome of social identity processes (Alimamy & Nadeem, 2021; Moulard et al., 2020). An endorsement can create an impression that fosters the perception of authenticity, as the third-party agents provide a more nuanced

perspective and play the roles of auditor and certifier (Carroll & Wheaton, 2009). Our hypothesis, therefore, posits:

H6. Endorsement credibility moderates the relationship between (a) media richness and perceived authenticity, (b) between parent brand attitude and perceived authenticity, and (c) between co-branding fit and perceived authenticity of an AI service app.

2.4. Value co-creation and intention to use

Value co-creation depends on user engagement and participation in the process (Alimamy & Nadeem, 2021). Companies provide a value proposition as their resource, and users provide their skills, knowledge, and capabilities in exchange (Vargo, Akaka, & Vaughan, 2017), where value co-creation occurs. Based on RET, this study conceptualizes authenticity as the “proper means” in the goal-pursuit process. In other words, users use the apps (e.g., the means) to eventually get the brand information and receive recommendations (e.g., the goal). Thus, when users can decide using proper and right means (e.g., the app is credible, humanlike, integrity, and symbolism), their attention is directed inward, enhancing the association with self and identity (Kirk, McSherry, & Swain, 2015). Engagement will occur, where the value of both brands and users could be exchanged and co-created.

Previous research has shown the relationship between positive algorithmic experience (e.g., fair, accountable, transparent, and interpretable) and the behavior (Shin, 2020b). When users perceive that the algorithm is fairer, more accountable, transparent, and explainable, they see it as more trustworthy and useful. This demonstrates that trust is of value to users and further implies the heuristic roles of algorithmic characteristics in terms of their underlying links to trust and subsequent attitudes toward algorithmic decisions (Shin, 2020b). The processes offer a useful perspective on the conceptualization of AI experience and interaction such as information disclosure, and intention to use (Shin, Zaid, Biocca, & Rasul, 2022).

H7. Perceived authenticity towards the AI service app positively relates to (a) value co-creation intention and (b) usage intention.

A fundamental goal of building an AI-powered service app is to create a touchpoint that could engage the target users (Mondal & Chakrabarti, 2021). However, the app could often be perceived as inauthentic; for example, it is developed to take users' data (Han & Yang, 2018). Therefore, marketers need to ensure users perceive the AI service app as authentic (e.g., it looks real, does what it claims, and does not exploit users). In other words, media richness, co-brand fit, and norms may not directly make users enjoy using the app, but they co-create value with it because they see it as authentic. This research hypothesizes that an AI-powered service app attempts to co-create value with users through its app factor (media richness) and brand factor (parent brand attitude and co-branding fit), mediated by the authenticity of the AI service app.

H8. Perceived authenticity mediates the relationship between (a) media richness, (b) parent brand attitude, and (c) co-branding fit and value co-creation intention.

H9. Perceived authenticity mediates the relationship between (a) media richness, (b) parent brand attitude, and (c) co-branding fit and usage intention.

3. Study 1 – Exploratory factor analysis (EFA)

Quantitative research is employed as a survey to provide a quantitative or numeric description of the respondents' trends, attitudes, or opinions (Hair, Black, Babin, & Anderson, 2019). Surveys and structural equation modeling have been used frequently in marketing research to test a causal relationship between two or more variables (Morales, Amir, & Lee, 2017). Many studies on mobile apps and AI technology have employed this method to verify the relationship between different

variables (Arghashi & Yuksel, 2022; Tran, Taylor, & Wen, 2022). Similarly, recent authenticity literature also uses this method to see the impact of authenticity on customers' cognitive, emotional, and behavioral outcomes (Alimamy & Nadeem, 2021; Morhart et al., 2015).

Study 1 explores the conceptualization of authenticity from a multidimensional perspective. Employing the EFA and CFA statistical method, this study validates four dimensions of authenticity in AI-powered service apps. EFA and CFA allow study 1 to define the underlying structure among the variables in the analysis (Hair et al., 2019), thus, preparing the scale for the subsequent studies.

3.1. Methods

With university ethics approval, this study targets consumers experienced with AI and healthcare technology through online questionnaires. We used convenience sampling due to the lack of a comprehensive user list. The Qualtrics survey was distributed via Facebook groups, two universities in Ho Chi Minh City, and an online tech community. These universities were chosen for their diverse, tech-savvy audiences and accessibility. Ho Chi Minh City, a technological and economic hub, is actively promoting AI development (An, 2024; MTA-Vietnam, 2024). The online community was selected for its tech focus, large membership, and non-student respondents. To minimize bias, we set quotas for gender, age, and education. Participants had to be over 18, familiar with AI technology, and have used healthcare tech in the past year. Data collection occurred from August to September 2022, yielding 331 useable responses, with 66% female and 57% young consumers, reflecting the demographic trend of AI users (Dharmaraj, 2019). Participants came from various industries and had diverse online habits (see Table 3).

All multi-item scales on a seven-point Likert scale are adopted from the existing scales in the literature that had demonstrated reliability and validity. The multidimensional scale of perceived authenticity is adapted from (Morhart et al., 2015), which includes integrity, credibility, and symbolism. For this specific study, the dimension of continuity is replaced by social presence, which is adapted from (Cheng & Jiang, 2020). The scale of fit is adapted from (Bigné et al., 2012)'s work on brand fit, and the scale of media richness is developed based on (Ferry, Kydd, & Sawyer, 2001; Hsieh & Lee, 2021). Parent brand attitude, endorsement credibility, and health consciousness are adapted from Jung and Kellaris (2006), Mai and Hoffmann (2015), and Thompson and Strutton (2012). The intention to use and value co-creation scales are adapted from Han and Yang (2018) and Alimamy and Nadeem (2021), respectively. For these scales, Cronbach's alpha ranges from 0.78 to 0.96, indicating high reliability for each construct (Hair et al., 2019).

We add questions to measure social desirability bias and performed common method bias tests in the later stage (Jozani, Ayaburi, Ko, & Choo, 2020). Both procedural and statistical methods are used to control common method variance (CMV) (Jozani et al., 2020). Since the data are collected through an online survey, a question randomization option is used that shows questions to each respondent in a shuffled manner. We use a common latent factor (CLF) test and compare the standardized regression weights of all items for models with and without CLF. The differences in these regression weights are significant, confirming that CMV is a major issue in our data (Gaskin, 2017). Thus, our structural model retains the CLF as our control variable.

3.2. Results

In this research, EFA is employed to explore the dimensions of authenticity. Confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling are conducted to verify the factor structure of a set of observed variables and assess the relationships among factors.

Table 3
The respondent's information.

	Frequency	Percentage		Frequency	Percentage
Age			Industry		
18–25	188	56.8	Health	3	0.9
26–34	81	24.5	Education	54	16.3
35–45	57	17.2	Entertainment	10	3.0
>45	5	1.5	Business	96	29.0
Gender			Technology	35	10.6
Male	113	34.1	Design	6	1.8
Female	218	65.9	Others	127	38.4
Online time/day			Mobile time/day		
0–4 h	131	39.6	0–4 h	92	27.8
4–8 h	133	40.2	4–8 h	177	53.5
> 8 h	67	20.2	>8 h	62	18.7

3.2.1. Exploratory factor analysis

Maximum likelihood and varimax are employed to maximize the differences between factors among different extraction methods (Gaskin, 2017). The matrix shows that the items are mostly grouped as expected. There is a cross-loading related to INTER_1 (“This app gives back to its consumers”), CRE_1 (“The app is believable”), and CRE_3 (“The app is honest”). SP_4 (“It treats me as a real patient”) has a low loading (below 0.5). After the cross-loading and low-loading items are subsequently removed, EFA is re-conducted. The new rotated factor matrix shows satisfactory loading scores. SP_3 shows relatively low loading but higher than the cut-off criterion (0.505) with the ratio of larger to smaller squared loadings is ignorable (2.4); therefore, it is maintained for further investigation (Hair et al., 2019, p. 155). Similarly, INTER_4 has a ratio of larger to smaller squared loadings greater than 0.20 – which can be ignored for interpretation purposes (Hair et al., 2019, p. 155) (see Table 4).

3.2.2. Measurement model, reliability, and validity

The CFA for 4-dimension authenticity produced a good fit (CMIN/DF = 1.674; CFI = 0.986; GFI = 0.955; TLI = 0.982; RMSEA = 0.045; SRMR = 0.033; PClose = 0.679). The final iteration removed six items, leaving thirteen final items in the model. Table 5 shows the good convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability of the model.

The current four-factor model is compared with the three-factor model (with symbolism and integrity combined due to their highest correlation) and the two-factor model (with credibility further

Table 4
Rotated Factor Matrix (Final solution).

Rotated Factor Matrix ^a	Factor			
	1	2	3	4
SP_1			0.901	
SP_2			0.657	
SP_3	0.325		0.505	
CRE_2	0.678			
CRE_4	0.739			
CRE_5	0.778			
CRE_6	0.613			
CRE_7	0.738			
SYM_1		0.665		
SYM_3		0.641		
SYM_4		0.704		
SYM_2		0.691		
INTER_2				0.634
INTER_3				0.678
INTER_4			0.338	0.554

Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Note(s): SP = Social Presence; CRE = Credibility; SYM = Symbolism; INTER = Integrity.

^a Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

combined with symbolism and integrity) to verify the best dimensional structure. The three-factor and two-factor models show poor fit with $\chi^2/df > 3$ and RMSEA > 0.08 . Thus, the four-factor model is maintained for further analysis.

The relationship between the dimensions and the second-order construct is significant ($p < 0.001$), and the factor loadings are higher than 0.5 (Table 6). H1 is confirmed.

4. Study 2 – Structural equation modeling (SEM) and fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis (FsQCA)

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a multivariate technique that examines a series of dependence relationships with a single analysis (Hair et al., 2019). SEM is employed in Study 2 to investigate the antecedents, moderators, and outcomes of authenticity.

FsQCA is a hybrid method that combines qualitative and quantitative approaches, identifying the complex combinations of causal conditions that lead to an outcome (Pappas & Woodside, 2021; Su, Chiang, James Lee, & Chang, 2016). This approach acknowledges that outcomes are often determined by many conditions rather than a single cause. By employing fsQCA, researchers can uncover multiple paths that lead to an outcome, providing a more nuanced understanding of complex phenomena, especially when human behavior is typically unlikely to follow a symmetrical stance (Chuah, Aw, & Yee, 2021).

This study employs fsQCA to reinforce the results of study 2 and explore the complex patterns of causal interrelationships between media factors (i.e., media richness), brand factors (i.e., co-branding fit and parent brand attitude), endorsement factors (e.g., endorsement credibility), and user factors (e.g., health consciousness) in determining users' authenticity perception.

4.1. Methods

Like the previous study, this study also targeted consumers with experience using AI and healthcare technology products. The data collection process occurred in October 2022. After the screening, 309 useable responses were retained. The sample comprised 67% females and 75% young consumers. The participants represented different industries, online and mobile time.

4.2. Results

We ran the CFA check for the whole model. The model fits well with Chi-square/df = 1.853, CFI = 0.913, SRMR = 0.066, RMSEA = 0.053, PClose = 0.140. The composite reliability (CR) and the H-coefficient are satisfied for further testing. All constructs have the square roots of AVE ranging between 0.76 and 0.85, which are higher than the inter-construct correlations. The value of MSV is found to be smaller than AVE.

The SEM results for the constructs' standardized path coefficients supports our hypotheses. Table 7 shows the standardized regression

Table 5
Convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability.

	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	SP	INTER	CRE	SYM
SP	0.857	0.601	0.596	0.867	0.775			
INTER	0.822	0.700	0.600	0.852	0.644***	0.836		
CRE	0.870	0.690	0.596	0.874	0.772***	0.692***	0.831	
SYM	0.879	0.645	0.600	0.882	0.729***	0.775***	0.656***	0.803

Note(s): **SP** = Social Presence; **CRE** = Credibility; **SYM** = Symbolism; **INTER** = Integrity; **AVE** = average variance extracted; **CR** = Composite Reliability; **MSV** = maximum shared squared variance; **MaxR(H)** = Maximum reliability; ***p < 0.001.

Table 6
Regression weights and standardized regression weights.

Relationship	Estimate	Standard Error	Critical Ratio	P-value	Standardized regression weights
AUTH → SP	0.903	0.077	11.783	a	0.785
AUTH → CRE	1.000				0.864
AUTH → INTER	0.924	0.070	13.143	a	0.866
AUTH → SYM	0.763	0.064	11.849	a	0.873

Notes: **SP** = Social Presence; **CRE** = Credibility; **SYM** = Symbolism; **INTER** = Integrity; **AUTH** = Perceived Authenticity.

^a p < 0.001.

Table 7
Regression weights.

Relationship	Standardized Estimate	Standard Error	Critical Ratio	P-Value	Notes
RICH → AUTH	0.448	0.036	7.732	***	H2 supported
BRAND → AUTH	0.277	0.062	4.229	***	H3 supported
FIT → AUTH	0.290	0.090	3.678	***	H4 supported
AUTH → VCC	0.671	0.096	7.988	***	H7a supported
AUTH → INT	0.640	0.076	7.076	***	H7b supported

Notes: **RICH** = Media richness; **BRAND** = Attitude towards parent brands; **FIT** = Co-brand fit; **VCC** = Value co-creation intention; **INT** = Usage intention; **AUTH** = Perceived Authenticity ***p < 0.001.

weights of the hypotheses at p < 0.05. The results confirm the positive influence of perceived richness ($\beta = 0.453, p < 0.001$) and co-branding fit ($\beta = 0.485, p < 0.001$) on perceived authenticity. Perceived authenticity also has a positive relationship with the intention to co-create value with the app ($\beta = 0.662, p < 0.001$) and the intention to use the app ($\beta = 0.641, p < 0.001$). The model fit is rechecked, which shows the acceptable fit.

The standardized values of three variables (co-branding fit, media richness, parent brand attitude and endorsement credibility) are created to examine the moderating role of endorsement credibility. **Table 8** shows that endorsement credibility strengthens the positive relationship between the fit and perceived authenticity ($\beta = 0.130, t\text{-value} = 2.112, p < 0.05$). There is also the negative moderating effect of endorsement credibility on the relationship between richness and perceived authenticity ($\beta = -0.070, t\text{-value} = -2.133, p < 0.05$). There is no moderating effect of health consciousness on the perception of authenticity.

The assessment of the indirect effects (mediation effects) of perceived authenticity in the proposed structural model is based on AMOS bootstrapping. For this statistical analysis, the indirect effects of 95% Bootstrap Confidence Interval bias corrected are performed. The perceived authenticity has been found to mediate the relationship between perceived media richness and intention/value co-creation,

Table 8
Moderating role of health consciousness and endorsement credibility.

Relationship	Path coefficient	Standard Error	Critical Ratio	P-Value	Notes
HC x RICH → AUTH	-0.010	0.021	-0.312	0.755	H5a rejected
HC x FIT → AUTH	-0.068	0.037	-1.466	0.143	H5b rejected
HC x BRAND → AUTH	0.017	0.035	0.382	0.703	H5c rejected
ZHC → AUTH	-0.071	0.030	-1.929	0.054	
EC x RICH → AUTH	-0.070	0.028	-2.133	0.033	H6a supported
EC x FIT → AUTH	0.130	0.025	2.112	0.035	H6b supported
EC x BRAND → AUTH	-0.007	0.034	-0.121	0.904	H6c rejected
ZEC → AUTH	0.160	0.033	3.848	***	

Notes: **RICH** = Media richness; **BRAND** = Attitude towards parent brands; **FIT** = Co-brand fit; **AUTH** = Perceived Authenticity; **HC** = Health consciousness, **EC** = Endorsement credibility; **ZHC** = standardized value of health consciousness; **ZEC** = standardized value of Endorsement credibility.

between perceived co-branding fit and intention/value co-creation. As the lower and upper levels are above “0,” indicating that the mediation effects are statistically significant, **H8a**, **H8b**, **H8c**, **H9a**, **H9b** and **H9c** are all confirmed.

4.3. fsQCA analysis

To further explore the SEM results, this study employed fsQCA (Version 3.0) to analyze the variables influencing authenticity. We calibrated three qualitative anchors of full membership (95% of data values), full non-membership (5%), and crossover point (50%) thresholds based on a 7-point Likert survey scale (Pappas & Woodside, 2021). The original values (from 5 to 1) were transformed into values ranging from 1 to 0. This study used five constructs: richness, co-branding fit, parent brand attitude, health consciousness and endorsement credibility. Next, this study used the “fuzzy truth table algorithm” function to calculate. Authenticity was an outcome, and the consistency threshold was set to 0.80 (Pappas & Woodside, 2021).

The fsQCA results in **Table 9** demonstrate a high consistency cutoff value of 0.883 and a high-consistency relationship among the constructs (0.85). The coverage score indicates that the explanatory power of the model is 77.9% for the 309 valid samples, exceeding the recommended threshold of 0.75 for good model fit (Su et al., 2016).

The fsQCA returns six configuration paths that lead to the high perception of authenticity among AI-powered service apps (**Table 9**). Solution 1 indicates that to foster a high perception of authenticity among consumers who have low scores on health consciousness, the apps should have high levels of parent-brand attitude and co-brand fit. Solutions 2 and 3 suggest that the combination of media factors (e.g., media richness), source factors (e.g., endorsement credibility), and brand factors (e.g., co-brand fit and parent brand attitude) can facilitate high perceptions of authenticity. Solution 4 shows that users with high levels of health consciousness also require an app with high media

Table 9
Results from fsQCA.

Solution	1	2	3	4	5	6
RICH		●	●	●		⊗
FIT	●	●			●	
BRAND	●		●	●	●	●
EC		●	●			⊗
HC	⊗			●	●	⊗
Raw coverage	0.315	0.510	0.485	0.469	0.448	0.135
Unique coverage	0.0389	0.017	0.0117	0.052	0.034	0.004
Consistency	0.950	0.980	0.980	0.969	0.945	0.886
Overall solution coverage	0.779					
Overall solution consistency	0.883					

Notes: *RICH* = Media richness; *BRAND* = Attitude towards parent brands; *FIT* = Co-brand fit; *AUTH* = Perceived Authenticity; *HC* = Health consciousness, *EC* = Endorsement credibility. Black circles (●) indicate the presence of a condition, and circles with “x” (⊗) indicate its absence.

richness and brand attitude. Solution 5 indicates the importance of brand factors among users with high health consciousness levels. Solution 6 indicates that to promote an app with low endorsement credibility among users who have low scores on health consciousness, high levels of parent brand attitude could stimulate the perception of authenticity, even without media richness.

5. Discussion

This study investigates the dimensions of authenticity in AI-powered service apps and identifies the antecedents of perceived authenticity. The research contributes to the understanding of authenticity’s measurement, drivers, consequences, and boundary conditions. The study provides insights into the nature of authenticity in digital touchpoints and highlights its significance for engagement theory and practice. The research integrates media, brand, endorser, and user factors into a single model to better understand consumers’ perceptions of authenticity. This study theoretically and methodologically contributes to the field of AI and marketing technologies by employing fsQCA, a novel analytical method gaining popularity in IS studies information systems (IS) studies (Chuah et al., 2021; Pappas & Woodside, 2021) but has yet to be applied in marketing technology research. fsQCA uses the asymmetrical approach to uncover how different combinations of media, brand, endorser, and user factors can better explain authenticity perception. This study builds upon prior research, which mainly conducted SEM to explore the symmetric relationships among factors related to authenticity perception (Alimamy & Kuhail, 2023). Given the intricate nature of user perception, a singular solution is unlikely to fully account for the phenomenon. Instead, multiple "causal recipes" are needed to capture the complexity and interconnections between various antecedents and outcomes.

This research extends recent efforts to measure authenticity from a multidimensional perspective. We confirm that the authenticity concept in the context of technology (1) goes beyond the notion of “someone likes us”, and (2) is a multidimensional concept that consists of four dimensions of social presence, credibility, integrity, and symbolism. Social presence is still an important factor in an AI-powered service app’s authenticity. In that sense, the AI-powered services should look like humans, have a natural voice, and could customize messages based on different customers’ needs (Cheng & Jiang, 2020). Such social presence may go beyond the design of the avatar (e.g., appearance, race, dress, gender) (Alimamy & Kuhail, 2023; Jones et al., 2022) and implies the whole interaction experience. For example, customers may feel as if they are interacting with a real human being through the question flow (e.g., how the virtual doctors set the order of diagnosis questionnaires) or explained recommendations (e.g., how the output is explained).

We find empirical data that authenticity in AI-powered services

needs to be credible. Align with previous research, credibility in this context can be understood to refer to the believability and trustworthiness of the generated information (Shin et al., 2024). As customers use AI-powered services to get health recommendations or product suggestions, they want to see the recommended items are trustworthy and dependable. As AI-powered services’ recommendations may cause uncertainty, they should be fair, accountable (e.g., identifying who is responsible for the recommendations), and transparent (e.g., explaining when and why AI algorithms produce personalized outcomes) (Shin, 2021).

In addition, integrity and symbolism are important app qualities to evaluate the app’s authenticity. It means that an authentic app needs to demonstrate that they are not biased by commercial motives, and positively impact what users think of themselves (Vo et al., 2022). This study builds on recent research on social chatbots, which defines authenticity as agency, autonomy, and uniqueness (Pentina et al., 2023). Authentic chatbots evolve uniquely through human interaction, creating a sense of reciprocal, real-time communication, and mutual information sharing (Pentina et al., 2023). Thus, balancing commercial interests and symbolic value is essential. Recent technology literature has failed to acknowledge these aspects as they prioritize humanlikeness when mentioning authenticity (Alimamy & Kuhail, 2023; Jones et al., 2022; Kuhail et al., 2022; Rese et al., 2020).

The results show that media richness acts as an important driver for authenticity. If they believe the app has a prominent level of media richness, the AI agent has body language, facial expressions, and a sense of presence, they will think the app is like an offline experience. This finding is consistent with the previous studies, which argue that media richness could affect behavioral intention (Chung et al., 2018; Hsieh & Lee, 2021). While in the context of influencers, users evaluate influencers’ authenticity based on their visibility and appearance (Lee & Eastin, 2021), media richness provides a cue for users to imagine the artificial humans they interact with. Consistent with existing qualitative research on technology-powered touchpoints (Wuenderlich & Paluch, 2017), this study finds that media/design factors, specifically media richness, play a significant role in shaping consumers’ perception of authenticity.

Co-branding fit is another factor that users consider crucial when evaluating authenticity. The collaboration between a parent brand and its partners will provide cues for evaluating the app’s intention. For example, if a hospital collaborates with a technology brand, users may think it is trying its best to provide the best version of its app. Therefore, they can prove their ability to accomplish the task (task attraction). In contrast, if a hospital brand partners with a fast-food brand, users may think this app is only built for commercial purposes, which may provide biased information for them to consume more fast food. Consistent with previous studies (Ilicic et al., 2018), the findings highlight that a touchpoint with a good fit with its partner could evoke consumer judgments toward its capability to provide credible information and meet users’ interests.

Regarding the outcomes of perceived authenticity, our study enhances the understanding of other marketing constructs, such as value co-creation. By exploring how perceived authenticity influences users’ intentions to co-create value, we address recent calls for further research on authenticity and engagement (Rosado-Pinto & Loureiro, 2020). Future studies could also investigate additional potential outcomes of perceived authenticity, such as subjective well-being (Rosado-Pinto & Loureiro, 2020) or brand relationship quality (Morhart et al., 2015).

Concerning the boundary conditions of authenticity, we expected that users with high health concerns would be less likely to see the app as authentic, as they could be skeptical of the recommendations. Surprisingly, the interaction results show that health consciousness does not significantly moderate the relationship between media/brand factors and the perception of authenticity. However, the fsQCA findings show that the combinations of different media factors (e.g., media richness) and brand factors (e.g., co-branding fit and parent brand attitude) will

be useful for users with low health consciousness scores. On the other hand, endorsement credibility is a critical condition for the perception of authenticity. This aligns with social identity theory, highlighting the influence of like-minded others or leaders' opinions, beliefs, and attitudes on users (Torres, Augusto, & Matos, 2019). In other words, users may rely on the endorser's credibility as a cue to form their perceptions of authenticity. Future research should explore additional moderators, such as the authenticity role in consumption needs and cultural socialization and examine its effects in individualistic versus collectivistic societies (Kumar & Kaushal, 2021).

5.1. Implications for theory

This study adds to the ongoing discussion on algorithmic experiences in marketing, which goes beyond basic digital capacity to consider the complex social and technical processes involved in algorithm creation, distribution, and consumption, as well as user control over these processes (e.g., data approval, privacy control) (Shin, 2020; 2021). In this vein, concepts such as humanness, happiness, fairness, accountability, transparency, trustworthiness, credibility, and explainability have been well-explored (Go & Sundar, 2019; Shin, 2020; 2021; Shin et al., 2017; Shin & Park, 2019). Our study extends this research vein by exploring the concept of authenticity as part of the algorithmic experiences, in which the understanding of the brand, the marketing offer, and the product allows users to make better decisions (e.g., value co-creation, intention to use).

The research further extends the heuristic-systematic model of the algorithmic process (HSM) (Shin, 2023). While our findings support that algorithmic factors such as fairness, accountability, and transparency are important heuristics, other brand- and self-related attributes could also be used during the evaluation. Social presence is the first available cue for customers to make sense of the AI-powered services, in which the design and style of the agent can inform its authenticity. Integrity is a brand-related heuristic that could change customers' evaluations, which is evaluated by the way the service takes advantage of their data (Jozani et al., 2020; Sax et al., 2018). We confirm that credibility is a key factor in systematic processing, as it requires complex analytics and thinking (Shin et al., 2024). In addition, symbolism should be considered when evaluating an AI-powered service, as it emphasizes the factor of self. Customers often reflect on their values and identities to enhance their algorithmic experience. When an AI algorithm makes a decision, whether it is accurate or not, customers need to feel that their values and identities are respected throughout the decision-making process. This means that the AI system should be transparent and considerate in its decision-making, considering the customer's perspectives and needs (Shin & Park, 2019).

Our findings contribute to theoretical advancement by propositioning what authenticity in the context of AI-powered services is made of, how it works, and what leads to this perception. Previous concepts of authenticity are not applicable to describe the uniqueness of customers' experiences of AI-powered services, because AI has been different from existing digital platforms. Unlike other studies that focus on originality and continuity of authenticity (Kumar & Kaushal, 2021; Morhart et al., 2015), this study highlights the role of social presence as one dimension of authenticity. The high amount of research in the context of brands (Kim et al., 2020), influencers (Lee & Eastin, 2021), and tourism (Mura, Tavakoli, & Pahlevan Sharif, 2016) have ignored the non-human humanlike touchpoints like AI-powered service apps. These apps involve a wide range of digital attributes (visualization, virtual assistant, ordering, and complaining services) that are not tangible to evaluate. AI service app is a new touchpoint, so users cannot evaluate how it connotes timelessness and historicity about a brand and its quality to go beyond trends. Instead, users will make a comparison to see how it pertains to the quality of the offline, assistant-like characteristics; thus, social presence is an important dimension in this construct.

Building on regulatory engagement theory, this study provides

empirical evidence for the impact of "proper means" on engagement strength and value experience. Despite many studies arguing that authenticity is an ethical behavior (Alimamy & Nadeem, 2021; Ilicic et al., 2018), this is the first study to conceptualize authenticity as a proper means in the goal-pursuit process. In addition, we have also confirmed the mediating role of the proper means (e.g., authenticity) in the engagement experience. Although this research focused on health services within the context of modern technology, future studies could explore the role of authenticity in other types of AI services (e.g., service robots, virtual assistants) across various contexts (e.g., education) and domains where authenticity is significant.

This study expands parasocial interaction theory by incorporating the concept of authenticity. While previous research has used this theory to understand user relationships with media characters (Han & Yang, 2018; Hsieh & Lee, 2021; Whang & Im, 2021), we focus on how users view AI service apps as credible and genuine companions. We also build on the ideas of physical and task attraction. Media technology can create convincing illusions of characters as real agents, enhancing perceived humanlikeness through media richness (Giles, 2002). Additionally, task attraction, which originally pertains to the ease of interacting with media characters (Rubin & McHugh, 1987), now relates to how well a co-brand fits with the product category and affects users' evaluation of the app's capabilities.

5.2. Implications for practice

Our research highlights key cognitive aspects of AI-powered services, showing that as more people interact with these technologies, they are increasingly aware of AI's potential drawbacks rather than just its capabilities. This study underscores the need for authenticity in AI-powered platforms, particularly in marketing, where trust and genuine engagement are crucial.

For practical applications, our findings suggest that AI-powered marketing services should prioritize authenticity to enhance customer experience and foster value co-creation. To engage customers effectively, AI service providers and marketers should focus on designing apps that genuinely connect with users. As customers continue to question the truthfulness, credibility and genuineness of AI, service providers should enrich their media channel, for example, by providing a virtual agent that could respond in human language and show their body language and facial expressions during the interaction. For example, a virtual doctor in healthcare should closely mimic real doctors in appearance and diagnostic procedures.

Additionally, ensuring authenticity through partnerships with relevant, marketers should pay attention to the brands they are collaborating with. To improve authenticity, the provider could partner with a relevant and credible brand in the field they are involved in. The shared values, objectives and collaboration benefits of the partnership should be clearly communicated. This transparency helps users understand the authentic nature of the partnership and reinforces the credibility of both brands.

Providers need to consider not just user-interface design, but also business objectives, customer needs, recommendation accuracy, monetization methods (e.g., data sales, advertising, subscriptions), and the way it represents customers' values. These insights can guide the development of other digital touchpoints, like chatbots and recommender systems.

Authenticity extends beyond simply encouraging initial app usage; it can significantly enhance user engagement and foster valuable co-creation behaviors. When managers perceive their apps as authentic, they can develop comprehensive marketing strategies that capitalize on this authenticity to drive deeper user interactions and collaborative value creation. For example, marketers can organize in-app events and provide users with opportunities to engage directly with the app's development team, share their experiences, and discuss future improvements. These interactive events can enhance the sense of

community and reinforce the app's commitment to customer engagement.

Our results provide some suggestions for the potential users' persona. Considering the moderating effect of injunctive norms, marketers should evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of their media richness and co-branding fit to decide their target audience. For example, the fsQCA shows the importance of different factors among users with high health consciousness levels. Therefore, marketers should understand their offers and categorize their customers. In the case of high health consciousness, marketers could choose to focus on (1) media richness and parent brand or (2) co-brand fit and parent brand. Similarly, in the case that their customers have no health consciousness, the parent brand attitude should be focused.

6. Conclusions

Our study is one of the first empirical research on authenticity and digital touchpoints, such as AI-powered service apps. Using the heuristic-systematic model of the algorithmic process (HSM), regulatory engagement theory, and parasocial interaction theory, we found that users' perceptions of authenticity are influenced by their social presence, credibility, integrity, and symbolism. These findings have significant theoretical and practical implications.

However, our study also has a few limitations. First, it was conducted in Vietnam, which has limited healthcare resources and a relatively low adoption rate of AI service apps. Future research should consider these cultural and contextual factors. Second, our sample is from big cities, which may limit the generalizability of our findings. Future research should aim to replicate our results with more diverse locations to ascertain the results reported here. In addition, the convenience sampling method may limit the generalizability of the findings, as it primarily captures responses from a specific demographic familiar with AI and healthcare technology. The focus on two universities and one online community might not fully represent the broader population. Future research should consider using diverse sampling methods and including a wider range of participants to enhance generalizability. Furthermore, while this study explored the impact of authenticity on user engagement, more outcomes and antecedents could be explored in the future such as socio-cultural factors. Future research could investigate how authenticity influences different AI services, such as service robots and virtual assistants, across various settings like education and other domains where authenticity plays a crucial role.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Diem-Trang Vo: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Long Van Thang Nguyen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Duy Dang-Pham:** Supervision, Methodology. **Ai-Phuong Hoang:** Supervision.

Ethics statement

This research has received ethics approval from RMIT University Ethics Committee (2022-24969-16785)

Ethics approval

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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